

Nickel-5-Nitro-1,10 Phenanthroline Complex*

S. C. Lahiri* and S. Aditya

The stability constant of Nickel-tris-5-nitro-1, 10 Phenanthroline complex has been determined spectrophotometrically. The value of $\log K_{stab}$ is 16.48 at 35°C.

Irving and Mellor^{1,2} studied the complexes of nickel ion with orthophenanthroline by the method of corresponding solution and also by the partition technique. Banks and Bystroff³ reported the presence of the 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes of nickel with 5-nitro-1, 10 phenanthroline by partition technique and reported a value of 20.4 for K_{stab} of the tris complex. We report in this communication the stability constant of the nickel-5-nitro-1 : 10 phenanthroline complex spectrophotometrically using the method of corresponding solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel perchlorate was prepared by dissolving Nickel carbonate (G.R.—E. Merck) in perchloric acid (G.R.—E. Merck) solution. The nickel content of the solution was estimated gravimetrically as nickel-dimethylglyoxime. Ferrous ammonium sulphate (G. R.—E. Merck) solution was prepared by direct weighing. All solutions were prepared with doubly distilled water.

All solutions for optical density measurements were buffered at pH=4.65 with 0.1M $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa} + 0.1\text{M } \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$, the ionic strength of the solutions being 0.1M.

Several sets of solutions were prepared. First set had solutions with constant iron content ($7.0 \times 10^{-5}\text{M}$) but increasing concentration of 5-nitro-1, 10 phenanthroline. Next set of solutions contained the same concentrations of 5-nitro-1, 10 phenanthroline and ferrous iron as in the first set and a known concentration of nickel ion. For different sets of measurements the concentration of $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ was varied.

The optical densities of the solutions at 510 m μ , the wavelength of maximum absorption of $\text{Fe}n\text{P}h_3^{2+}$ (where n-Ph is 5-nitro-1 : 10 phenanthroline) were measured at 35°C. Similar to $\text{FeP}h_3^{2+}$ and $\text{FeP}h_2^{2+}$, as observed by Kolthoff *et al.*⁴, $\text{Fe}n\text{P}h_3^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}n\text{P}h_2^{2+}$

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**Present address : Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Nadia.

1. H. Irving and D. H. Mellor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3457.

2. H. Irving and D. H. Mellor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 5222.

3. C. V. Banks and R. I. Bystroff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 6133.

4. I. M. Kolthoff, D. H. Leussing and T. S. Lee, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2173.

do not have any appreciable absorption in this region. Fig. 1 gives curves of optical densities for different sets of solutions plotted against increasing concentration of 5-nitro-1 : 10 phenanthroline.

FIG. 1

From these curves, the formation number, i.e. the number of nitrophenanthroline molecules per nickel atom, has been calculated over the range of concentrations of nickel ions and nitro-*o*-phenanthroline. This is found to be 3. Thus it is seen that under our experimental conditions (at an ionic strength of 0.1 M and pH equal to 4.65) nickel ion is present almost exclusively as $Ni(n-Ph)_3^{2+}$. As such there will be very little error if the stability constant of the tris-complex is calculated with no correction for the presence of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complex. Under the condition, the calculations of the constant for 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 complex would not be possible as they might be present, if at all, in negligible amounts. So no attempt has been made to determine the stabilities of $Nin-Ph^{2+}$ and $Nin-Ph_2^{2+}$. Only the stability constant of $Nin-Ph_3^{2+}$ has been calculated from the present measurements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As already stated the optical density reading at 510 m μ is only due to $Fe(\pi-Ph)_3^{2+}$. So if the extinction coefficient of nitroferroin at 510 m μ is known, its concentration can be easily had from the optical densities.

Thus we have

$$[Fen-Ph_3^{2+}] = d/\epsilon \quad \text{where } d = \text{optical density} \\ \epsilon = \text{the extinction coefficient,}$$

$$\text{and} \quad [Fe^{2+}] = [Fe^{2+}]_{\text{Total}} - [Fen-Ph_3^{2+}].$$

Therefore, the concentration of free ($\pi-Ph$) can be calculated, the stability constant of nitroferroin being known.

$$[K_{\text{instab. (nitroferroin)}}] = 1.01 \times 10^{-15} \text{ at } 35^\circ$$

$$\text{and} \quad \epsilon_{510 \text{ m}\mu} = 11785 (\pm 64)]^7$$

Now,

$$[Ni(n-P_h)_3^{2+}] = \frac{[n-P_h]_{total} - [n-P_h]_{free} - 3 [Fe(n-P_h)_3^{2+}]}{3}$$

and $[Ni^{2+}]_{free} = [Ni^{2+}]_{total} - [Ni(n-P_h)_3^{2+}]$.

Thus the dissociation constant of the nickel-tris-nitrophenanthroline complex

$$K_{Ni(n-P_h)_3^{2+}} = \frac{[Ni^{2+}] [n-P_h]^3}{[Ni(n-P_h)_3^{2+}]}$$

can be calculated. Table I presents the results. The average value of the dissociation constant of the complex comes out to be 3.3×10^{-17} or $\log K_{stab}$ 16.48 at 35°C.

Banks and Bystroff reported a value of 20.4 for $\log K_{stab}$ of the nickel-tris complex at 25°C at an ionic strength of 0.1 M using partition technique. This value is at 25°C and is a rough one (as the authors claim). As such a comparison of Banks and Bystroff's values with the present determination is not justified. Nevertheless the difference is too large. This possibly due to the fact that these authors used for pK_{nitro}-orthophenanthroline the value given by Brandt and Gullstrom⁵ which is too high. We may calculate the stability constant of nickel-tris-nitro-o-phenanthroline complex on the basis of the relationship proposed by Irving and Rossotti⁶.

$$\log K_{MP_3} = \log K_{MQ_3} + 3 (\log K_{HP} - \log K_{BQ}),$$

TABLE I

Temperature—35°C Ionic Strength—0.1M			Wavelength—510 mμ pH—4.65		
Total Concentration of					
Fe ²⁺ × 10 ⁵	5-nitro-1:10 phenanthroline × 10 ⁵	Ni ²⁺ × 10 ⁵	O.D.	Ni (n-Ph) ₃ ²⁺ × 10 ⁵	K _d (n-Ph) ₃ ²⁺ × 10 ¹⁷
7.0M	15.0M	2.1M	0.323	1.970M	4.249
7.0	15.0	2.8	0.250	2.625	2.900
7.0	15.0	3.5	0.185	3.204	2.672
7.0	14.0	1.4	0.355	1.346	3.034
7.0	14.0	2.8	0.214	2.607	2.846
7.0	14.0	3.5	0.153	3.164	2.419
7.0	17.5	1.4	0.483	1.359	4.266
7.0	17.5	2.1	0.410	2.021	3.865
7.0	17.5	2.8	0.340	2.651	3.944
7.0	17.5	3.5	0.272	3.295	3.062

Average K=3.33 (+.25)×10⁻¹⁷

5. W. W. Brandt and D. K. Gullstrom, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3532.

6. H. Irving and H. Rossotti, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, 10, 72.

where K_{HQ} and K_{HP} are dissociation constants of different ligands HQ and HP and K_{M^2} and K_{M^3} the stability constants of the complexes. Taking 23.8^{10} for $\log K_{stab}$ of nickel-tris ortho-phenanthroline, 3.25^7 for $pK_n P^{\Delta H^+}$ and 5.06^8 for $pK P^{\Delta H^+}$ we would expect a value of 18.3 for pK_{stab} of nickel-tris nitrophenanthroline complex at 25°C . If we assume that the temperature coefficient of stability constant of the nickel-ortho-phenanthroline complexes is the same as that for the ferrous ortho-phenanthroline complexes, then we would expect a value of $pK \approx 17.0$ at 35°C for Ni-nitrophenanthroline complex. The $\log K_{stab}$ from the present determination is pretty close to this value.

Since $Nin\cdot P^{\Delta_3^+}$ are likely to have the same size, the same entropy change of formation would be expected in both cases. The greater stability of the $Nin\cdot P^{\Delta_3^+}$ may be due to greater enthalpy change associated with the reaction which would be reflected in the free energy term.

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DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
CALCUTTA-9.

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